

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF GAMES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY TO ADULT LEARNERS

Joldasbaeva Palzada Axmetovna

A junior teacher of Kimyo International University in Tashkent

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7655498>

Abstract. Vocabulary is essential for building knowledge of a new language. It provides basis for learning structures and grammar. Without vocabulary it is not possible neither to communicate nor improve in language. Well acquired vocabulary ensures a good start to a successful learning process culminating in good knowledge of language and ability to use it well in real life. As a consequent, the article presents the investigation of teaching vocabulary to adult learners by using games. The result of the research shows that the use of games in teaching vocabulary are both suitable and interesting for adult learners.

Keywords: English language, vocabulary, games, adult learners, Jeopardy games, the recipe game.

Introduction. Vocabulary can be defined as words we must know to communicate effectively; words in speaking and words in listening. Ur states: "Vocabulary can be defined, roughly, as the words we teach in the foreign language. However, a new item of vocabulary may be more than just a single word: for example, post office, and mother-in-law, which are made up of two or three words but express a single idea. A useful convention is to cover all such cases by talking about vocabulary "items" rather than "words"[6].

Hornby defines vocabulary as "the total number of words in a language; vocabulary is a list of words with their meanings"[2].

Adult students are completely different form children or adolescent students. Compared to younger group of students, adults do not need that much demonstration but ask for more explanation and formulation of principles. They are matured, their intelligence has already developed. They went through a whole educational system and they dispose of rich personal experience. They have also developed specific habits and have specific expectations [1, p.105-112]. Adults are in many cases not really interested in language, but in what they do through it. That is to say, adult students view language as an instrument for doing other things.

Teaching vocabulary through the use of games help to decrease the level of student's affective filter and also, to perform successfully the activities developed in the classroom in which student's levels of anxiety and shyness are brought into a minimum. Therefore, there are some effective games in teaching vocabulary to adult learners [4].

Jeopardy game is a version of the popular board game. It's a fun and easy to play quiz game, and it's great for reviewing vocabulary and certain grammar forms. It ranks alongside Taboo as one of the most played games in the TEFL classroom. It's a great way to round off the week or to save for the last day of the course.

For playing this game, teachers need five separate categories of questions and for each category five or six questions ranging in difficulty from easy (\$100) to difficult (\$600). First, a teacher draws the Jeopardy grid on the board as in the above diagram. Write the categories horizontally and long the top divide the columns into increments of one hundred of the local currency up to either five or six hundred depending on how many questions / how long you have. Split students into teams of three or four, with two or three teams being optimal. If teachers have different color board markers or chalk, give each team a separate color. If that's not possible, assign each team their own symbol instead, e.g. circles, Xs, or triangles. The first team starts and chooses a category and an amount, depending on how confident they are in being able to answer the question. Read out the question. If the team answers correctly then put a tick in the appropriate grid square with that team's color, or alternatively mark the square with their symbol. If the team answers incorrectly, the square stays open and another team or the same team can attempt to answer it in a later round. Write a one or two-word reminder of the question or maybe a drawing in the space to help students keep track of the open questions. Now, move on to the next team who can either choose a new question and amount or attempt to answer a question which was previously incorrectly answered.

This recipe game is fun activity lets adult learners get creative while practicing food vocabulary and presentation skills.

For playing this game, a teacher puts students into pairs or threes and tell them that they are going to write a shopping list, then write on the board or dictate the following list.

- a green vegetable
- another vegetable
- a type of meat or fish
- a tin of something
- a jar of something
- something salty
- something sweet
- a dairy product
- a herb or spice

In groups, students choose one food item that fits each category. When everyone has finished, collect the shopping lists and randomly redistribute them so that each group has a different group's list. Students now have 15 minutes to come up with a three-course meal using only the ingredients on their shopping list (plus salt, pepper and cooking oil). When the time is up, a teacher tells the groups that they must take it in turns to present their menu to the other students, encourage them to make each course sound as appetizing as possible. Finally students all vote on which menu they would be most willing to eat.

Conclusion. English plays a key role in human lives. It is nowadays considered to be an inevitable part of general education for people practically all over the world. Having at least basic knowledge of it is more or less necessary for everyone. Therefore, one should know the vocabulary of English language so as to communicate effectively in English language. Consequently, the article showed the importance of learning and teaching vocabulary. The result of the research showed that mentioned games helped adult learners to decrease the level of their affective filter and also, to perform successfully the activities developed in the classroom in which their levels of anxiety and shyness were brought into a minimum.

References:

1. Cameron, L. (2003). Challenges for ELT from the expansion in teaching children. *ELT Journal*, 57(2), 105–112
2. Hornby, A. S. *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary*, Oxford University Press 2000, ISBN 0-19-431585-1.
3. Nation, I. S. P. (1990). *Teaching and learning vocabulary*. Boston, Mass.: Heinle&Heinle Publishers
4. Nguyen & Khuat(2003). The effectiveness of learning vocabulary through games. *Asian journal*
5. Thorburry, S. (2002). *How to teach vocabulary*. England: Pearson Education Limited.
6. Ur, P., (1998). *A course in language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.